

Degradation of NCF-Epoxy Composites containing Voids

F. Gehrig, E. Mannov and K. Schulte
Technische Universität Hamburg-Harburg,
Institute of Polymers & Composites
Denickestr. 15, 21073 Hamburg
Germany
florian.gehrig@tuhh.de

SUMMARY

The degradation under single axial fatigue loading of non crimp fabric composites is influenced by manufacturing defects as voids, fibre misalignments and poor resin wetting. A fast model has been developed by Gagel et al. to predict the fatigue life in accordance with micro damage mechanisms [1]. Experimental investigations of NCF based fibre composites containing voids were performed in order to identify the model parameters and to extend the present model of Gagel et al. to be as well capable for manufacturing defects. Voids were found to be not in the fibre bundles but in the resin rich domains of the NCF. A pronounced reduction of the fatigue life is stated for stress ratios of $R=0.1$ and $R=-1$. Fatigue of voided specimen was found to improve fatigue life at $R=-1$. and is explained by the influence of the voids on the interlaminar crack development and the resulting crack density. The cracks especially close to bundles have a detrimental effect on failure mechanisms as e.g. stress intensity on fibre bundles critical in load direction especially close to final failure of the composite. The experimental data were used to improve the present model and to identify these parameters which include the micromechanical damage induced by voids.

Keywords: Fatigue, degradation, fatigue life prediction, voids, NCF (Non Crimp Fabric).

Introduction

Today composite manufacturing faces the problems of high production rates. Large parts like wind turbine blades or aircraft structures are build, but manufacturing defects can not be banished. Especially during liquid infusion processes voids, misalignments or poor resin wetting can be observed. The repair or scrap of large and cost intensive parts is economically not feasible. Therefore it is mandatory to have reliable life prediction models for defected composite parts available in order to estimate the influence of defects on fatigue life.

The resin transfer moulding techniques are very efficient in producing large parts at comparable low cost. However the process can lead besides other manufacturing defects as fibre waviness to voids and/or porosity. The void formation occurring when using RTM techniques are well described in [2-4].

The degradation process of glass-fibre vinyl ester laminates was study under static tension by Varna et al.[5]. The transverse loaded specimens degraded by the formation of intensive small transverse cracking dependent and large cracks which were almost

independent of the void content. Prakash et al. proposed an explanation of degradation based on local fibre buckling at void position and matrix softening [6]. Seiler et al. showed a study on porous unidirectional glass polymer matrix specimens for leaf springs. The fatigue life was significantly decreased when tested in shear loading in the presence of 5.9 vol.% of voids [7]. In [8-10] fatigue tests were performed in tensile and 3-point bending loading giving a decreasing trend when voids are present. Further investigations are still in progress but up to now composite fatigue models are not providing parameters to adjust defects which were induced by the processing.

Today's models for the prediction of the fatigue life are based on [11-13]. The model of Gagel et al. introduces the micro damage mechanisms, e.g. interlaminar cracking and combines them with the experimentally determined life time. The model is described in more detail in [1]. However, the model can predict the degradation expressed by the loss in dynamic stiffness due to interlaminar cracking which provides an estimation of the stiffness degradation over 80% of the life time. That includes the phase I and II dominated by transverse cracking of the S-N curve and excludes the fibre failure dominated phase III.

A distinct difference has to be made between defects and damage because this is mixed up in the past studies [14]. Damage is here defined as a mechanical or thermal load induced plastic deformation or crack. The defects are defined as morphological disorders, like misalignments or voids or holes.

This work deals with the experiments that will give the parameters for the model development. During fatigue the visible damage was recorded by means of interlaminar cracks in 90°, 45° and 0°. The phenomena observed will be discussed in context with the presence of voids as a defect.

Experimental procedure

A glass fibre non crimp fabric type F was infiltrated by a VARTM process with an epoxy resin. The Lay-up is described in detail by [1]. During the infusion process a certain amount of air was introduced by a bypass to create voids in the later solidified composite as shown in Figure 1. A study of the morphology of these voids in size, geometry and location was performed, and different discrete sizes and locations were identified. A cut and polished cross section is shown in Figure 2. The voids are clearly visible between the filaments of the NCF in resin rich areas.

The resulting specimens had a large scatter in void content. As Figure 2 to Figure 4 show different void volumes and can range from zero to about 2.5 vol. % (low void content) to 8.8 vol. % (high void content).

Figure 1: Voids in VARTM processed NCF glass fibre laminate left. Zoom in an detailed view of the yarn structure on the right side.

The plates were glued with load transfer elements and cut to $250 \times 25 \text{ mm}^2$ by a diamond blade. The tested gage length for fatigue tests with $R=0.1$ and $R=-1$ were 150mm. For $R=10$ the specimens were 130mm with free gage length of 10 mm.

Figure 2: Cut off of a specimen with high void volume.

Figure 3: Cut off a specimen with low void volume.

Figure 4: Cut off a specimen without voids as a reference.

The fatigue tests were performed on a Schenck Instron 100kN or 63kN servo hydraulic testing machine at a frequency of 6Hz. The crack densities were studied by interrupting the fatigue test at distinct load cycles and taking transmission light micrographs.

Results

The results are unconventional plotted not by the maximum stress but by the difference of stress amplitude. Under tension-tension fatigue ($R=0.1$) the fatigue life is reduced due to the presence of voids (Figure 5). A large scatter is observed and can be related to the scatter of void volume of the particular specimen.

Figure 5: S-N- curves for GF-NCF-EP with voided and reference material in tension-tension mode (R=0.1).

Figure 6: S-N- Curves for GF-NCF-EP with voided and reference material in compression-compression loading (R=10).

For compression-compression fatigue (R=10) the influence is less pronounced but still shows a negative trend and shorter fatigue life time for specimens containing voids (Figure 6). The behaviour for the tension-compression fatigue (R=-1) is plotted in Figure 7. The experimental data show an extended life for coupons containing voids.

Figure 7: S-N- Curves for GF-NCF-EP with voids and reference in tension-compression loading (R=-1).

Figure 8: Development of the crack density in phase I of fatigue life versus load (R=0.1).

The degradation of the NCF at R=0.1 takes place by forming interlaminar cracks in the 90°- and 45°-layers. Figure 8 shows the transverse crack density developed in phase I of the fatigue life for laminates containing different amounts of voids. After the first load cycle no cracks were observed in the reference material whereas numerous transverse cracks appeared in voided specimens. At 1000 cycles a drastic increase in the number of cracks could be observed in the reference material and went towards saturation with increasing load cycles, like for the voided specimens.

The Figure 9 plotted the crack development for the reference and a high void volume containing coupon in R=-1 for coupons at the same number of load cycles. It is

remarkable that the reference contains in all layers more cracks than it was observed for the specimen with voids. This can indicate a faster degradation process which is already mutual for final failure at low loads. Whereas lower cracking at higher loads for the void containing coupon is leading to failure.

Figure 9: Development of the crack densities of the different layers vs. the number of cycles for the reference and a high void volume containing specimen ($R = -1$).

Figure 10: Degradation parameter D_i vs. life time at various maximum load conditions for $R = -1$ and high void volume in the specimens.

The degradation parameter D_i is defined as the percent loss of the dynamic young's modulus defined in the following equation:

$$D_i = \frac{E_{dyn}^0 - E_{dyn}^i}{E_{dyn}^0} \quad \text{equation 1}$$

Figure 11: : Degradation parameter D_i vs. life time for reference of fatigue tests performed at $R=-1$.

Figure 10 and Figure 11 show the degradation as a measure of stiffness reduction vs. normalized fatigue life for voided and reference specimens. The break down of degradation inside a data set is attributed to the interruption of the test for taking the pictures for crack density measures. The degradation in voided specimens shows a good trend with higher load levels and increasing strain rate. The lower the maximum stress the more pronounced are the degradation phase I at the beginning. The linear steady state in phase II and the final progressive failure in phase III of the material vanish with increasing maximum load. For the reference material large scatter in the degradation curves is found. But an overall trend for the load level dependence like for the voided specimens can be seen. For low loaded specimens it can be seen in phase III that for both reference and voided specimens bundle failure occurs which leads not to immediate final failure but provokes rapid degradation. In case of higher loads the sudden death of the specimen occurred and no particular phase III was documented.

Discussion

The S-N curves in $R=0.1$ fatigue indicate lower fatigue life by the presence of voids. The reason may be the initial crack density development which as well allows failure dominating delamination growth in the interlayer between 0° and 45° rowing. Due to the voids are present in tension more cracks are formed due to stress intensities at the voids already in the early state of fatigue life. Due to the fact that voids have a considerably low effect on tensile strength of 0° fibre dominated coupons the fibres are not directly disturbed by the voids [15]. But the fatigue degradation is matrix dominated and dependent of the initiation and growth of interlaminar cracks.

In R=10 fatigue the specimens fail after the development of 0° cracks in the outer layers. Due to the reduced shear stiffness by the presence of voids and locally reduced support of the neighbouring layers it can be assumed that kinking can be initiated prior the reference material. Also the fast occurrence of longitudinal cracks corroborates this assumption of a loss of stability in the vicinity of voids.

The picture for R=-1 is completely different to the previous load cases. If the matrix yielding is considered the locally present voids reduce internal stresses. The load levels in R=-1 fatigue are lower than in R=0.1 or R=-1 for the respective direction. But the load amplitude is up to double as high. As presented in Figure 9 the crack density development is considerably lower and can be stated as well for both reference and defect containing specimens at same load level.

However, the measure of interlaminar cracking and the degradation via measure of dynamic stiffness can be described by a parameter depending of the presence of voids. This can be drawn because a dependence of the material behaviour was found from the presence of voids. However, the Young's modulus of the coupons was not found as being influenced by the voids and moreover strongly fibre content dependent.

Model

The degradation model is based on the empirical assumption to analyse the stiffness evolution during fatigue. The evolution of the transverse crack density results in the degradation of the dynamic Young's modulus. In the case of manufacturing defects the initial composite stiffness is different and is introduced into the model of Gagel et al. 1 by an initial defect parameter D_0 .

$$D_i = D_{i-1} + \Delta D_i + D_0$$

were D_i is the damage parameter at a specific load step, D_{i+1} the damage parameter of the prior load step and ΔD the change of damage in one load step. Due to the previous discussion the initial defect parameter is rather low in fibre dominated NCF lay-ups.

The damage parameter is a function of the transverse crack development ρ (TCD). The initial Young's modulus can be calculated by using stiffness models of Mori-Tanaka and the classical laminate theory [16]. The TCD ρ is dependent on the void content and is changing with each load increment i :

$$\rho_i = \rho_{i-1} + \Delta\rho_i + \Delta\rho_v$$

$\Delta\rho_v$ is the transverse crack density introduced by voids during one load cycle. ρ_{i-1} is the TCD of the previous load cycle and $\Delta\rho$ the increase of transverse cracks in the load cycle. The model and the integration will be discussed elsewhere. As can be seen from the experiments the additional crack density is positive for R=0.1 and R=10, but seems to be negative for R=-1. However, further integration of the parameters have to be investigated in future.

Conclusion

The fatigue life under R=0.1 and R=10 was investigated and stated as being reduced by the presence of voids. The effect of this behaviour is due to the transverse cracking

behaviour and the locally low support of the void surrounding material and pure compressive loads. For tension – compression the interlaminar cracking seems to be drastically reduced by the presence of voids and therefore extends fatigue life. The experimental data gathered can now be implemented in the proposed model extension for the Gagel et al. model to introduce a fatigue life prediction with respect of manufacturing defects.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We kindly thank the German Research Foundation DFG (contract Schu 926/15-1) for financial support.

References

- [1] Gagel A, Schulte, K., "*Non-Scalar Approach to Simulate the mechanical Degradation Process in Fibre-Reinforced-Polymers (FRP's)*", ASTM STP 1436 Composite materials: testing and design, 14th volume. ASTM International, West Conshohocken, PA, (2003), p.238–251.
- [2] Ruiz E, Achim, V., Soukane, S., Trochu, F., Bréard, J., "*Optimization of injection flow rate to minimize micro/macro-voids formation in resin transfer molded composites*", Composites Science and Technology, 66, (2006), p.475–486.
- [3] Labordus M, Pieters, M., Hoebergen, A., Söderlund, J., "*The causes of voids in laminates made with vacuum injection*", Innovative process and material solutions for creative design effectiveness. SAMPE Europe, Aalsmeer, Netherlands, (2000), p.433–441.
- [4] Hamidi YK, Aktas, Levent, Altan, M. Cengiz, "*Three-dimensional features of void morphology in resin transfer molded composites*", Composites Science and Technology, 65, (2005), p.1306–1320.
- [5] Varna J, Joffe, R., Berglund, L. A., Lundström, T. S., "*Effect of voids on failure mechanisms in RTM laminates*", Composites Science and Technology, 53, (1995), p.241–249.
- [6] Prakash R, "*Significance of Defects in the fatigue failure of Carbon-Fiber reinforced-plastics*", FIBRE SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY, 14, (1981), p.171–181.
- [7] Seiler U, "*Zur Auslegung statisch und dynamisch belasteter Bauteile aus Verbundwerkstoffen am Beispiel von GFK-Blattfedern*", Dissertation der Fakultät für Maschinenbau RWTH-Aachen, Aachen, (1987).
- [8] Dill CW, Tipton, S. M., Glaessgen, E. H., Branscum, K. D., "*Fatigue Strength Reduction Imposed by Porosity in a Fiberglass Composite*", ASTM STP 1128, (1992), p.152–162.
- [9] Chambers A.R., J.S. Earl, C.A. Squires, M.A. Suhot, "*The effect of voids on the flexural fatigue performance of unidirectional carbon fibre composites developed for wind turbine applications*", International Journal of Fatigue, 28, (2006), p.1389–1398.

- [10] Suhot MA, Chambers, A. R., "*The Effect of Voids on the Flexural Fatigue Performance of Unidirectional Carbon Fibre Composites*", ICCM-16 International Conference on Composite Materials (CD-ROM), Kyoto, (2007), p.19.
- [11] Broutman LJ, Sahu, S., "*A New Theory to Predict Cumulative Fatigue Damage in Fiberglass-Reinforced Plastics*", ASTM STP 497 Composite materials testing and design, Philadelphia, Pa., (1972), p.170–188.
- [12] Chou PC, "*Cumulative damage model for advanced composites*, Ohio, Final Report, AFWAL-TR-84-4004, (1984).
- [13] Diao X, Ye, Lin, Mai, Yiu-Wing, "*A statistical model of residual strength and fatigue life of composite laminates*", Composites Science and Technology, 54, (1995), p.329–336.
- [14] Bishop, Sarah M., "*AGARD-R-690 The significance of defects on the failure of fibre composites*", AGARD, (1981) , ISBN 92-835-1410-9.
- [15] Olivier P, Cottu, J. P., Ferret, B., "*Effects of cure cycle pressure and voids on some mechanical properties of carbon/epoxy laminates*", Composites, 26, (1995), p.509–515.
- [16] Park JY, Zureick, A. H., "*Effect of filler and void content on mechanical properties of pultruded composite materials under shear loading*", Polymer Composites, 26, (2005), p.181–192.